

TRAFFIC PREDICTION AND OPTIMIZATION THROUGH DEEP EXTREME LEARNING MACHINE

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1. Literature Review

For the purposes of optimizing the traffic prediction and vehicle lane change decision-making, deep extreme learning machines (DELIM) are being established. Through thorough investigation of neural networks in machine learning, it has been determined that traditional neural networks such as Back Propagation (BP) neural network have susceptibility to slow learning and a tendency of being trapped on local optima. Peng and Xiang while building a Genetic Algorithm (GA) optimized BP neural network for short-term traffic prediction used a wavelet denoising and phase space reconstruction for data preprocessing [1]. The results of this study show that the proposed GA-BP model performs well in terms of Mean Absolute Percent Error (MAPE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE).

To tackle the issues presented by traditional neural network architecture, deep learning has emerged as a promising research area. Due to multiple hidden layers, it helps in the hierarchical extraction of features. The typical feedforward neural network has remained a huge bottleneck in its application across different studies. To improve upon this, Huang, et al. [2] proposed a novel learning method named Extreme Learning Machine (ELM) which randomly chooses hidden nodes and analytically finds the weights of Single-Hidden Layer Feedforward Neural Networks (SLFNs). This model has found significant applications in different fields of research. Some of the applications of ELM are mentioned below.

Table 1: Application of ELM approach in various fields [3]

Area/Field	Authors	Brief Description
Finance	Markovic et al. [4]	ELM was used to forecast Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The results demonstrated that ELM has superior capability of forecasting GDP growth rate.
Finance	Milacic et al. [5]	ELM was applied to predict GDP growth rate and its performance was compared to Backpropagation approach. Results show that ELM is a better method for this application.
Finance	Kordanuli et al. [6]	GDP and Hirschman-Herfindahl Index (HHI) forecasting are performed through ELM and BP approaches. The inputs for GDP included agriculture, industry, and expenditure of general government.

Finance	Rakic et al. [7]	e-GDP (Electronic GDP) is estimated and calculated by ELM by providing inputs such as trade in services, exports and imports.
Finance	Das et al. [8]	This study devised an exchange rate prediction model using On-Line Sequential Extreme Learning Machine (OS-ELM) along with Krill Herd (KH) algorithm.
Agriculture	Turkoglu and Hanbay [9]	ELM was utilized with Local Binary Patterns (LBP) to recognize the plant species based on the features extracted from the leaves.
Port Industry	Li et al. [10]	This research provided an insight on monthly container throughput forecasting using Secondary Decomposition (SD) learning approach integrated with ELM.
Physics	Ahmad et al. [11]	Environmental Sound Classification (ESC) is performed through Optimum Allocation Sampling (OAS) based Empirical Mode Method (EMD). ELM classifier was used to evaluate the performance of the proposed method. Sound classification involves recognizing the origin of a particular sound.
Economics	Xu et al. [12]	Carbon Emission Trading is a form of a trading framework for carbon dioxide (CO ₂) and other greenhouse gases (GHG). This study presented a carbon pricing predictor using time series network analysis and ELM algorithm.
Mechanical Engineering	Miao and Zhao [13]	This research designed a unique approach to predict the residual strength of defective pipelines using Deep Extreme Learning Machine (DELIM) with the Hybrid Teaching-Learning-based Optimization (HTLBO) algorithm.
Calculus	S. M et al. [14]	In this study, the authors proposed a neural network method based on ELM approach for solving fractional Differential Equations.

As discussed earlier, one of the methods employed in this research is swarm intelligence optimization. These algorithms have become a prominent area of interest for researchers and engineers due to their varying applications. Different studies have implemented these optimization techniques in conjunction with other methods for predicting, estimating or forecasting different parameters. Few examples are mentioned below.

Table 2: Research studies related to the application of swarm intelligence optimization method [3]

Area/Field	Authors	Brief Description
Solar Energy	Reddy et al. [15]	Solar Radiation prediction by weather forecast data is performed by an Elephant Herd Optimization method with a DELM (EHO-DELM) model.
Environmental Sciences	Song and Yao [16]	This study confronts the prevention and control of water pollution problem. This is done by predicting water quality by integrating Synchrosqueezed Wavelet Transform and DELM with the Sparrow Search Algorithm (SWT-SSA-DELM).
Chemistry / Electronics	Jia et al. [17]	DELM with the help of Improved Sparrow Search Algorithm (ISSA) is constructed to accurately predict the state-of-health of lithium-ion batteries (LIBs). This prediction can help in enhancing the performance and ensuring the safety of battery storage system.
Chemistry / Electronics	Zhang et al. [18]	Working on estimating the state-of health of lithium-ion batteries, this study proposes an online method combining Sparrow Search Algorithm (SSA) and DELM. The results show that this technique predicts accurately, provides good stability and adaptability.
Wind Energy	An et al. [19]	Wind power data is non-linear and non-stationary in nature. Therefore, improving the predicting performance of wind power system is particularly challenging. This research uses Particle Swarm Optimization-Variational Mode Decomposition (PVMD) and DELM to provide a robust short term wind power prediction method.
Chemistry / Electronics	Gao et al. [20]	An improved Grey Wolf Optimizer is used in this research to optimize the DELM (CGWO-DELM) for predicting the remaining useful life of lithium-ion batteries.

The deep extreme learning machine hasn't yet found much popularity in the domain of vehicle transportation. There are limited amount of studies done in this area. Siddiqui et al. [21] discussed the implementation of Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and DELM to predict the optimum parking location in an area. Zhu et al. [22] presented a comprehensive review of control strategies of connected and autonomous vehicles on a freeway in their journal article. Similar to Zhu's research, Yue et al. [23] studied the effects of connected and autonomous vehicle merging algorithms on the behavior of human-driven vehicles. A study introduced the DELM approach to empower vehicles with making intelligent route decisions [24].

2. Methodology

The information utilized in this project originated from cameras installed on different roads throughout Singapore [25]. These cameras were deployed to capture images with the aim of extracting records on traffic volume. The image capture frequency is set at intervals of 5 minutes, and advanced techniques for image extraction are applied to derive the traffic volume data.

Figure 1: Data preprocessing and VMD workflow in the model development [3]

Figure 2: Model Construction of PSO-DELM and HHO-DELM [3]

2.1. Autonomous lane changing behavior

Autonomous lane changing involves autonomous vehicles evaluating the conditions of the self-driving vehicle, surrounding vehicles, and road traffic data. This analysis is utilized to create safe and logical lane changing commands, with the goal of establishing a favorable driving space environment and fulfilling overall driving objectives. The decision-making process for the autonomous lane changing behavior in these vehicles focuses on generating motivation for lane changing and selecting the target lane.

The incentive to initiate lane changes predominantly stems from a large number of vehicles on the current lane, causing a decline in vehicle speed and dissatisfaction among drivers. To enhance the driving environment and swiftly achieve the driving objectives, autonomous vehicles formulate intentions to change lanes.

Figure 3: Autonomous lane change decision-making [3]

3. Dataset Description

The dataset provided (see Appendix A) focuses on traffic cameras and contains essential information regarding their operation. The data is timestamped for example "2023-12-08T03:18:40+08:00" and includes details about individual traffic cameras, their images, locations, unique IDs, and image metadata. This dataset is extracted from Land Transport Authority of Singapore [25].

Each entry in the dataset represents a specific set of data related to a traffic camera. This includes timestamps, images, location coordinates, camera IDs, and image metadata. The unique IDs (e.g., 1001, 1002) identify each camera, and their data includes a timestamp, image URL, location coordinates, camera ID, and image metadata.

The "image" field contains the URL of the captured image, the "location" field includes latitude and longitude coordinates, and the "camera_id" field serves as a unique identifier for each camera. Image metadata includes height, width, and an MD5 hash for content uniqueness.

This dataset can be valuable for reducing traffic congestion in the following ways:

1. **Real-Time Traffic Monitoring:** Authorities can monitor current traffic conditions and identify congested areas in real-time using live images.
2. **Traffic Pattern Analysis:** Historical data enables the analysis of traffic patterns, aiding in understanding and predicting congestion trends.
3. **Dynamic Traffic Routing:** Real-time data supports dynamic route adjustments to distribute traffic efficiently, reducing congestion in specific areas.
4. **Emergency Response and Incident Management:** Quick detection of incidents aids emergency responders in managing traffic flow around incidents, minimizing disruptions.
5. **Public Communication:** Real-time updates based on the dataset inform commuters about traffic conditions, enabling informed decisions on routes and travel times.
6. **Infrastructure Planning:** Historical data guides long-term infrastructure planning, identifying areas for improvement and optimizing road networks.
7. **Policy Decision Support:** Data insights can help policymakers assess and develop effective traffic management policies.

8. **Public Transport Optimization:** Real-time traffic data aids in optimizing public transport routes and schedules, encouraging sustainable transportation options.

In summary, this dataset provides comprehensive real-time and historical data on traffic conditions. Leveraging this information can empower authorities to make informed decisions, implement effective policies, and optimize transportation systems to reduce traffic congestion.

3.1.Data Cleaning

This program (see Appendix B) defines a function `clean_traffic_data` that takes the path to a JSON file as an argument, loads the data, and performs the specified cleaning steps. In the `__main__` block, it uses the function to clean the traffic data from the provided JSON file and prints the cleaned DataFrame.

4. Upcoming Milestones and Future Plan

As the methodology for the research has been established and dataset is acquired, now we plan to implement the model on the dataset. The goal is to optimize the traffic volumes through the Deep Extreme Learning Machine algorithm and optimized its parameters with Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Harris Hawks Optimizer (HHO). The performance of the two methods will be compared with each other on the basis of few parameters such as Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and R-Squared (R^2). An additional target for the project is to predict autonomous vehicle lane change behavior with the VMD-PSO-DELM and VMD-HHO-DELM. To achieve this, a driver dissatisfaction model has to be built.

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Appendix

A

Traffic Images Data (.txt file)

```
{
  "items": [
    {
      "timestamp": "2023-12-08T03:18:40+08:00",
      "cameras": [
        {
          "timestamp": "2023-12-08T03:17:20+08:00",
          "image": "https://images.data.gov.sg/api/traffic-images/2023/12/1e1486c9-
dad3-431b-8463-bbe93d287d62.jpg",
          "location": {
            "latitude": 1.29531332,
            "longitude": 103.871146
          },
          "camera_id": "1001",
          "image_metadata": {
            "height": 240,
            "width": 320,
            "md5": "4e2434982d075150bad8c1c8040f7e7b"
          }
        },
        {
          "timestamp": "2023-12-08T03:17:20+08:00",
          "image": "https://images.data.gov.sg/api/traffic-images/2023/12/c1a8c965-b44a-
41d1-8db4-925a029c7eb6.jpg",
          "location": {
            "latitude": 1.319541067,
            "longitude": 103.8785627
          },
          "camera_id": "1002",
          "image_metadata": {
            "height": 240,
            "width": 320,
            "md5": "4eb6f3be1a94ccabc4c6307081737e77"
          }
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "timestamp": "2023-12-08T03:17:20+08:00",
```

```
    "image": "https://images.data.gov.sg/api/traffic-images/2023/12/53c3ca9e-06f6-444b-8830-11c4b4214ed6.jpg",
    "location": {
      "latitude": 1.323957439,
      "longitude": 103.8728576
    },
    "camera_id": "1003",
    "image_metadata": {
      "height": 240,
      "width": 320,
      "md5": "75dbb786e70fff223dcb38ce6226f3ae"
    }
  }
}
{
  "timestamp": "2023-12-08T03:17:20+08:00",
  "image": "https://images.data.gov.sg/api/traffic-images/2023/12/c41e595e-59b2-4e4d-b893-a2ee9732ba17.jpg",
  "location": {
    "latitude": 1.365434,
    "longitude": 103.953997
  },
  "camera_id": "1111",
  "image_metadata": {
    "height": 1080,
    "width": 1920,
    "md5": "9bce110a6460b444a853e88cd7e624a1"
  }
}
```

Appendix

B

Data Cleaning Program

```
import json
import pandas as pd
from urllib.parse import urlparse

def clean_traffic_data(json_file_path):
    # Load data from the JSON file
    with open(json_file_path, 'r') as file:
        traffic_data = json.load(file)

    # Extract camera data
    cameras_data = traffic_data.get("items", [])

    if not cameras_data:
        print("No camera data found in the provided JSON.")
        return

    # Create a DataFrame from camera data
    df = pd.DataFrame(cameras_data[0].get("cameras", []))

    # Convert timestamp strings to datetime objects
    df["timestamp"] = pd.to_datetime(df["timestamp"])

    # Handle missing metadata by replacing NaN values with an empty dictionary
    df["image_metadata"] = df["image_metadata"].apply(lambda x: {} if pd.isnull(x)
    else x)

    # Extract domain names from image URLs
    df["image_domain"] = df["image"].apply(lambda x: urlparse(x).netloc)
    # Drop unnecessary columns
    df = df.drop(["image_metadata"], axis=1)
    return df

if __name__ == "__main__":
    # Replace 'your_dataset_file.json' with the actual file path
    json_file_path = 'traffic_data_singapore.json'
    # Clean the traffic data
    cleaned_traffic_data = clean_traffic_data(json_file_path)

    # Display the cleaned DataFrame
    print(cleaned_traffic_data)
```